

MODELING APPROACH OF MICROBUCKLING MECHANISM DURING CURE IN A CARBON EPOXY LAMINATE

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SUMMARY : In this work, the mechanism of fibre positioning imperfections observed in carbon epoxy composites is studied. The fibre waviness is established as being the consequence of a fibre microbuckling phenomenon created by resin shrinkage during the hot phase of the thermosetting reaction instead of final cooling stage of cure process. In order to have a good description of this fundamental mechanism, both experimental and theoretical studies on single fibre composite specimens are done. The physical and mechanical aspects of the thermosetting reaction are established for the 120°C isothermal cure. The structure is described through a model of a fibre embedded in an infinite matrix medium and which is generalized to the case of laminates. The microbuckling possibilities are analyzed through a matrix response determined experimentally during its cure by a DMTA method.

KEYWORDS : Waviness Defects - Cure Process - Microbuckling during cure - Single fibre Composite Specimen - Gelation - Shrinkage – Long Fibre Laminate – Viscoelasticity.

INTRODUCTION

Several years of research on the compressive strength of long fibre composite have allowed the comprehension and modeling of compressive failure mechanisms. Authors have shown that the appearance of fibre microbuckling phenomenon triggers the compressive failure. This mechanism is controlled by the physical non-linearity of the matrix as well as by the presence of initial fibre positioning imperfections. More precisely, the fibres, which are initially wavy, bend under compressive loading. The matrix by opposing to this displacement, becomes plastic but, if its stiffness is not high enough, a kinking band appears suddenly. Fibre initial waviness is then a real representative indicator of initial residual stress state existing in the composite. This cannot be neglected in any design of modern structures. Therefore, the efficiency of any large computing time approach is directly conditioned by the knowledge of initial fibre positioning imperfection characteristics : wavelength and amplitude.

Indeed, it is possible to develop measurement techniques to describe fibre initial defect. A variety of techniques have been proposed over the years for inferring the true 3D structure of the fibre-reinforced composite material. However, all of these techniques can only be done on finished cured sample using complex and heavy instrumentation. There is therefore on one hand, a need for fibre initial undulation description and, on the other hand, interest in solutions to avoid them.

Among the many experimental techniques to describe the fibre positioning inside of a composite, a very realistic one for a long-fibre reinforced ply composite has been established by Paluch [1]. For this purpose, he has rebuilt the three dimensional progress of carbon fibres within the ply by a succession of cross cuttings (figure 1).

Fig. 1 : Perspective view of carbon T300 fibres in an 914 epoxy matrix.

It results from this observation that the carbon fibre defects are very closed to a sinusoidal form. This has also been observed on single fibre composite specimens by Ahlstrom [2] and Grandsire [3] and it suggests us clearly that fibre waviness results from a microbuckling instability mechanism which appears during the hot phase of composite cure cycle. The question is to know where the instability occurs during the cure step of process.

Some authors, like Grandsire [3], have supposed that the instability appears during the final cooling down phase. As a theoretical point of view, the mechanism which generates the instability may be due to the difference of axial thermal dilatation between epoxy matrix and fibre (high strength carbon fibre), whose thermal dilatation coefficients are around $11E-5^{\circ}C^{-1}$ and around $-0.02E-5^{\circ}C^{-1}$ respectively. Therefore, during the cooling phase, the fibre dilates axially while the matrix contracts. According to the coherence of the fibre-matrix interface, a compressive loading is thus generated onto the fibre. As this phenomenon occurs at hot temperature, one can consider that the support provided by the matrix to the fibre is still limited and can not avoid fibre microbuckling. This point of view was explained in a previous paper [4]. The matrix behavior change during cooling was taken into account and thermal stress applied onto the fibre was compared with the necessary one to start microbuckling instability. Results show that thermal stress was never able to trigger fibre microbuckling phenomenon during cooling. This was confirmed by single fibre cure tests carried out with different cure cycles but having the same final cooling stage. It appears clearly that the instability is essentially due to the resin thermosetting reaction since the two cycles used have the same final cooling down phase and that microbuckling only occurs in case of a fast cure cycle. Thus, thermosetting reaction must be analyzed under a mechanical point of view to search for microbuckling possibilities.

A description of physical and mechanical behaviors of an LY556 epoxy resin during its thermosetting reaction is presented in this paper. In order to grasp fundamental aspects of

microbuckling instability, our modeling approach was tested on the case of a single carbon fibre embedded in an infinite matrix. Both elastic and viscous effects are taken into account. A generalization is then proposed for the case of long fibre laminates.

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE THERMOSETTING REACTION

According to previous results, the fibre defect generation can be explained as being a warm phase microbuckling phenomenon. In fact, during cure process, volume variation, generated by the chemical reaction of thermosetting, is done under a shrinkage form. This chemical reaction corresponds to phase change from liquid viscous state to solid state. The shrinkage may then induce a compressive loading onto the fibres. Since the matrix is at a viscous state, it provides only a limited support to the fibre. This mechanism is not obvious to study because, on one hand, mechanical characteristics of the resin are changing strongly during chemical reaction and, on the other hand, in a laminate composite, the thickness thermal gradient generated by the exothermic aspect of the reaction triggers different conversion rates at each point of the material. Moreover, data about volume shrinkage generated by thermosetting reaction are rare in the literature and must still be confirmed in order to set a predictive modeling.

Matrix modulus and volume variations are temperature dependent. The temperature variations affect volume shrinkage through thermal expansion of matrix obtained previously. Thus, since thermal expansion is cancelled for isothermal cure, the shrinkage measured gives a direct representation of the one induced by the corresponding chemical reaction. The case of an isothermal cure, for example 120°C, is therefore analyzed in detail.

Physical aspects : T.T.T. cure diagram

In order to provide an useful framework for understanding and conceptualizing changes that occur during the cure of our thermosetting system, the corresponding isothermal Time-Temperature-Transformation (T.T.T.) diagram is plotted on figure 2.

Fig. 2 : Epoxy LY 556 T.T.T. Cure Diagram

This kind of diagram depicts the various physical state of a thermoset (liquid, rubber and glass) in relation to two phenomena of critical importance : gelation and vitrification.

Between $T_{g\ gel\ point}$ and $T_{g\ \infty}$, for example at 120°C, the isothermal viscous liquid changes to a viscoelastic fluid, then to a rubber (gelation reaction) and finally to a glass (vitrification

reaction). The S-shaped curve indicates the onset of vitrification, which represents the time at which the glass transition temperature of the reacting system has reached the isothermal temperature of cure. $T_{g\infty}$ is the glass transition temperature of a fully cured resin, above which the system is a rubber in its fully cured state. $T_{g\text{ gel point}}$ represents the lowest cure temperature that will result in a material with elastomeric properties, below which the solid formed will be an ungelled glass. Below T_{g0} , the unreacted resin remains an ungelled glass with low chemical reactivity.

Thus, this T.T.T. cure diagram shows us that isothermal 120°C phase change corresponds to the transition from a viscoelastic fluid state to a rubbery state through gelation reaction. The degree of cure corresponding to the gelation reaction, that signifies the start of the irreversible transformation from a liquid to a rubber, can be calculated for thermosetting systems where the chemistry is known. The Flory relation [5] is used to determine the degree of cure at the gel point (α_{gel}). Thus, for our thermosetting system, $\alpha_{\text{gel}} = 55\%$. This gel point can then be localized by D.S.C. analysis applied onto the 120°C isothermal cure.

Mechanical aspects : D.M.T.A. analysis

In order to specify physical and mechanical behaviors of epoxy resin during its thermosetting reaction, measurements of the shear stiffness variation have been carried out with a Dynamic Mechanical and Thermal Analysis (D.M.T.A.) system under a configuration of torsion. An automatic control on torsion plates to have a vanishing axial force applied onto the resin sample has allowed us to confirm the shrinkage aspect of the chemical thermosetting reaction. Using different frequency analysis, the resin viscoelastic behavior during the chemical reaction can be characterized finely.

Results displaying modulus and shrinkage variations are plotted versus degree of cure, in order to identify gelation reaction. This reaction, as explained before, corresponds to the liquid – rubber phase change and therefore owns volume variation characteristics (figures 3-a to 3-d).

Fig. 3-a : Epoxy loss modulus complete evolution for 120°C isothermal cure

Fig. 3-b : Epoxy elastic modulus complete evolution for 120°C isothermal cure

Fig. 3-c : Epoxy loss modulus evolution during 120°C isothermal cure

Fig. 3-d : Epoxy shrinkage evolution for 120°C isothermal cure

gelation for 120°C isothermal cure

120°C isothermal cure (Ciba-Geigy)

Figures 3-a, 3-b and 3-c show that the thermosetting reaction acts quickly because of a fast modulus growing up. This reaction owns a real viscoelastic behavior for both gelation and vitrification steps (figures 3-a and 3-c). Figure 3-d, by help of Ciba-Geigy epoxy resin manufacturer information, confirms shrinkage behavior of thermosetting reaction and especially during gelation reaction. Fast modulus evolution and D.M.T.A. apparatus resonance phenomenon during viscous liquid state don't allow to have a more rich frequency description. However, these experimental analyses provide a minimal knowledge in order to set the basis of a good modeling.

INSTABILITY MODELING IN CASE OF SINGLE FIBRE SPECIMEN

In a first time, and in order to grasp correctly microbuckling mechanism, the cure of a single fibre composite specimen is studied. In this case, the fibre is supposed perfectly bounded with an infinite matrix medium. Two kinds of approaches are presented. The first one, based on the fact that thermosetting reaction acts quickly, can be done under elastic behavior considerations. The second one is placed into viscoelastic framework since this behavior cannot be neglected.

Elastic approach

In this context, the stability equations were written by Minahen and Knauss, [6]; Waas, [7] and are described as following :

$$E_f h \frac{d^2 u^f}{dx^2} + \tau^b - \tau^t = 0 \quad (1-a)$$

$$\frac{E_f h^3}{12(1-\nu_f^2)} \frac{d^4 v^f}{dx^4} + P \left(\frac{d^2 v^f}{dx^2} + \frac{d^2 v_0^f}{dx^2} \right) + \sigma^b - \sigma^t + \frac{h}{2} \left(\frac{d\tau^b}{dx} + \frac{d\tau^t}{dx} \right) = 0 \quad (1-b)$$

The functions $u(x)$ and $v(x)$ denote respectively fibre axial and transverse displacement. E_f and h are respectively the Young modulus and the fibre thickness. σ^t , σ^b , τ^t and τ^b are respectively the top side and bottom side normal and transverse stress components applied by the epoxy resin onto the fibres. P denotes the axial compressive load applied onto the fibre. These governing equations are further simplified by assuming the fibre displacement to be of cosinusoidal and sinusoidal form like :

$u_f = U_f \cos(\alpha x)$ and $v_f = V_f \sin(\alpha x)$, where U_f and V_f denote fibre displacement amplitudes in longitudinal and axial direction and $\alpha = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$ is the wave number (λ being the wave length).

Bhalerao and Moon [8], using fibre linear elasticity, have evaluated the unknown reactions σ^b , σ^t , τ^b and τ^t imposed on the fibre by the matrix. In our work, microbuckling possibilities are searched in case of an initial straight fibre ($V_f^0 = 0$). Thus, following simplifications outlined earlier, the 1-b stability equation becomes :

$$-\alpha^2 \mathbf{P} + \alpha^4 \frac{E_f h^3}{12(1-\nu_f^2)} + 2\alpha B_2 E_m + h\alpha^2 B_4 E_m = 0 \quad (2)$$

Where $B_2 = [2(1-\nu_m) + \alpha \frac{h}{2}(1-2\nu_m)] \frac{1}{D}$, $B_4 = [(1-2\nu_m) + \alpha h(1-\nu_m)] \frac{1}{D}$ and $D = (1 + \nu_m)(3-4\nu_m)$

The coefficients B_2 , B_4 are constants defined by Bhalerao and Moon that are depending on matrix characteristics and on wavenumber α , ν_m is the matrix Poisson's ratio.

This relation between the applied axial compressive load P and the wavenumber α corresponds to the description of a neutral stability curve. Thus, the minimum of this stability curve will lead to the critical axial load and critical corresponding wavenumber for a fibre transverse displacement searched under sinusoidal form.

Finite elements calculations are used in order to verify if the fibre axial applied load, induced onto the fibre during the thermosetting stage of the cure, may be superior to the critical one that will generate fibre microbuckling. In this context, CAX 8 axisymmetric elements were employed to describe a single 60mm fibre length (fibre diameter 0.007mm) embedded into an 8 mm thick matrix.

These finite elements calculations, using volume shrinkage and corresponding elastic material modulus during chemical reaction of phase change, have given following stress pattern along the fibre for several volume shrinkage strain (figure 4-a). The corresponding load can then be compared with the critical one for microbuckling instability as shown below (figure 4-b).

Figure 4-a : Fibre compressive stress pattern during resin thermosetting reaction

Figure 4-b : Comparison between fibre axial applied load and critical microbuckling load during resin thermosetting reaction

The elastic approach of fibre stability shows real microbuckling possibilities. The instability may occur nearly the gelation state of the resin cure, as indicated on figures 4-b and 3-d. The corresponding wavelength for the reach of instability was then found between 4800 and 1600 μm .

Viscoelastic approach

As seen before on fig. 3-a and 3-c, epoxy resin chemical reaction owns a real viscoelastic behavior that cannot be ignored. In this context, Bhalerao and Moon works, about the growth

of waviness for a perfectly bounded fibre in a viscoelastic infinite matrix, were used again. Using nondimensionalizing (nd) notation for wavelength $\lambda_{nd} = \frac{\lambda}{h}$, wavenumber $\eta_{nd} = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_{nd}} = \frac{k}{\lambda_{nd}}$, fibre amplitude V_{nd}^f and for axial load $P_{nd} = \frac{P}{hE_f}$, they express the stability equation for a perfectly bonded elastic fibre in a viscoelastic matrix as :

$$\left[\frac{2B_2}{\eta_{nd}} + B_4 \right] \int_0^t r_{ve}(t-\xi) \frac{dV_{nd}^f(\xi)}{d\xi} d\xi + \left[\frac{\eta_{nd}^2}{12(1-\nu_f^2)} - P_{nd}(t) \right] V^f(t) = P_{nd}(t) \quad (3)$$

Where the kernel $r_{ve}(t-\xi) = \frac{E_m(t)}{E_f}$ of the integral is the nondimensional matrix relaxation modulus.

The dominant wave number is obtained by evaluating the extremum of the Carson Transform of equation 3. So, they propose an evaluation of the bifurcation dominant wavelength λ as :

$$P_{nd} = \frac{k^2[(10\lambda_{nd}^2 + 3k^2)(1-\nu_m) + 6k\lambda_{nd}(1-2\nu_m)]}{12\lambda_{nd}^2(1-\nu_f^2)(1-\nu_m^2)(2\lambda_{nd}^2 - k^2)} \quad (4)$$

However, the difficulty is to evaluate the real viscoelastic load applied onto the fibre. The matrix viscoelastic behavior must first be evaluated in order to compute fibre applied axial load.

Therefore, using D.M.T.A. analysis, Cole-Cole diagrams were established to compare our plots with the usual one of standard viscoelastic models. Note that only few frequencies could be tested (frequencies shown in D.M.T.A. curves, fig. 3-c) in order to avoid DMTA apparatus resonance during resin liquid viscous state.

Typical Cole-Cole plots of the resin during gelation and vitrification reactions are shown on fig. 5-a and 5-b.

Fig. 5-a : Typical Cole-Cole plot of the epoxy LY556 resin nearly the gelation reaction.

Fig. 5-b Typical Cole-Cole plot of the epoxy LY556 resin during the vitrification reaction.

Vitrification Cole-Cole plot can easily be identified as being a Zener parabolic model. But, since instability may occur nearly the gelation step of the cure, we must focused ourselves on the corresponding kind of behavior. These S curves for Cole-Cole plots are unfortunately not corresponding to known classical viscoelastic models. The assumption is then made that it could be approached, in a first time, by a Voigt modeling. It means that the elastic shear modulus is supposed being independent from the loss modulus G'' .

In the context of a perfectly bounded fibre embedded in an infinite matrix, fibre applied strain can be written as a function of time under following form :

$$\varepsilon_f(t) = \frac{E_m \varepsilon^{vol} + \eta \frac{d\varepsilon^{vol}}{dt}}{E_m + E_f} [1 - \exp(-\frac{E_f + E_m}{\eta} t)] \quad (5)$$

In case of elastic fibre strain, the applied load is then directly given by the Hooke relation

$$P(t) = E^f \frac{\varepsilon_f(t)}{S_f} \quad (6)$$

Thus, by substituting equation 6 into equation 4, and solving for wavelength λ , we found a bifurcation dominant wavelength around 2300 μm during resin shrinkage. This is the smallest bifurcation wavelength being possible in comparison with fibre maximal strain authorized before tensile rupture (1.4%). Wavelengths observed on single fibre specimens for the same isothermal cure are between 220 and 480 μm , depending on the thermal gradient present in our oven. Unfortunately, our modeling approach for both elastic and viscoelastic frameworks does not provide wavelength magnitude order in comparison with the experimental one. Of course, our viscoelastic modeling of the matrix behavior is rather poor, since Voigt approach doesn't allow relaxation, but other reasons exist to explain this mismatch between experimental and analytical wavelengths. A first reason is that we do not take into account postbuckling phenomenon, especially during the final cooling down step. A second reason may be that we have inadequately estimated the interaction between fibre and matrix through a poor description of tensile and shear matrix response.

APPLICATION FOR LONG FIBRE LAMINATE

D.M.T.A. results have given strong informations to describe microbuckling mechanism in case of a single fibre embedded in an infinite matrix. An extend is now proposed for long fibre laminates which are corresponding to more realistic application forms for carbon epoxy systems. Experimental analysis, done on fully cured laminates by Schuerch, have shown that, if fibre volume fraction is greater than 25%, fibres waviness is presented under a co-operative form. This in phase waviness corresponds to usual laminates since fibre volume fraction is generally around 60% to 70%. In this context, Grandidier et al. [9] have established that the microbuckling mechanism results from a co-operative fibre waviness affected by the zero degree ply thickness and the staking sequence. This taken into account of microscopic and macroscopic effects is similar to a simplified Cosserat homogeneous medium. For the same reasons that in the single fibre case, the elastic approach is first developed. The viscoelastic approach is actually under investigation for more realistic constitutive law than the Voigt modeling.

Elastic approach

In this framework, the instability is driven by the following differential equation :

$$E_f \frac{d_f}{4} \frac{\partial^4 v}{\partial x^4} - \left(\frac{G_m}{f(1-f)} - \sigma_f(y) \right) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} - \frac{E_m}{f(1-f)(1-v_m^2)} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (7)$$

where $v(x,y)$ denotes fibres transverse displacement field in the unidirectional ply (x for fibre axial direction and y for transverse direction). Coefficients E_f , d_f , E_m and G_m are respectively fibre Young modulus, fibre diameter, matrix Young and shear modulus, and f represents fibre volume fraction. The displacement field is searched under a classical sinusoidal form like :

$$v(x,y) = V(y) \sin(\alpha x) \quad (8)$$

Equation 7 becomes then :

$$B \frac{d^2 V(y)}{dy^2} + CV(y) \quad (9)$$

$$B = \frac{-E_m}{G_m(1-\nu_m^2)} \quad C = \alpha^2 \left[\frac{f(1-f)\alpha^2 E_f r_{gf}^2}{G_m} + 1 - \sigma_f \frac{f(1-f)}{G_m} \right] \quad r_{gf} = \sqrt{\frac{I_f}{S_f}}$$

Where I_f is fibre quadratic moment and S_f fibre section.

For a ply inside of a laminate, displacement field is clamped at top and bottom interfaces with neighboring plies. Following boundary conditions for $V(y)$ are then imposed : $V(H)=V(0)=0$, where H denotes ply thickness.

Thus, according to equation 9, $V(y)$ can be searched under following form : $V(y) = A \sin(kh)$ where k denotes the ply transverse wave number. By taking into account previous boundary conditions, fibre displacement into a bounded-bounded ply of a laminate can be written as following :

$$v(x,y) = A \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{H} y\right) \sin(\alpha x) \quad (10)$$

By replacing this in equation 8 and solving for fibre stress σ_f we find :

$$\sigma_f = \left[\frac{1}{\alpha^2} \frac{\pi^2 E_m}{f(1-f)h^2(1-\nu_m^2)} + \frac{G_m}{f(1-f)} + \alpha^2 E_f r_{gf}^2 \right] \quad (11)$$

σ_f is a function of the wavenumber. This represents a neutral stability curve again, so that the instability will be reached for the lowest fibre stress σ_f defined by this equation, where the wavenumber α is the variable. The critical wavenumber is obtained by evaluating the extremum of σ_f with respect to α as : $\frac{d\sigma_f(\alpha)}{d\alpha} = 0$

This condition leads us to following expressions for critical wavelength and corresponding fibre stress :

$$\alpha_{\text{critical}} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{E_m}{E_f(1-\nu_m^2)f(1-f)}} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{H r_{gf}}} \quad (12-a)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{fibre critical}} = \frac{G_m}{f(1-f)} + \frac{2\pi r_{gf}}{H} \sqrt{\frac{E_m E_f}{(1-\nu_m^2)f(1-f)}} \quad (12-b)$$

On figure 6 we have plotted the critical wavelength obtained, by application to an usual 0.2mm thick ply inside of a laminate cured isothermally at 120°C with several fibre volume fraction.

Fig. 6 : Fibre critical wavelength for a 0.2mm thick ply cured isothermally at 120°C with several fibre volume fraction (LY 556 epoxy resin).

Paluch's experimental analysis has established that T300 carbon fibres microbuckling wavelengths were between 1240 and 2320 microns. Our first elastic approach is therefore in the right magnitude order for wavelength description.

Nevertheless, a good approach of microbuckling phenomenon cannot be done without taking into account cure time, temperature and viscous effects on the growth of waviness. The final objective is also to have an evaluation of the waviness amplitude.

CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

In this work, the modeling of microbuckling instability establishes that fibre waviness really occur during thermosetting reaction. Using DSC and D.M.T.A. analysis, instability is shown as being generated by shrinkage strain evolution taking place near gelation step. This approach provides a reliable basis to the comprehension and prediction of waviness imperfections appearance occurring in laminates. In case of single fibre specimens, elastic approach has shown the microbuckling possibilities, but the obtained wavelength does not agree with the experimental results. The accuracy of any approach depends strongly of the viscoelastic constitutive law since viscous effects cannot be neglected, as shown by experimental modulus curves. However, in order to describe more finely the microbuckling instability and to have a better estimation of the critical wavelength, we still need, on one hand, more precisions about the viscoelastic constitutive law and, on the other hand, an improvement of the interaction description between fibre and matrix. Indeed, even nearly critical tensile rupture strain of carbon fibre, the viscoelastic wavelength found is too high. Concerning our approach in case of long fibre laminates, the elastic wavelength found is close to the experimental one. This accuracy is explained by the influence of the ply thickness that represents a natural parameter for a laminate. However, thermal gradient existing in laminates during cure must also be taken into account since it will generate different cure rate and therefore different degree of conversion, each one with a different shrinkage strain. Post buckling during the final cooling down step of the cure cycle must also be analyzed.

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